

Supplementary Material for Research Paper “Explainability Needs in Agriculture: Exploring Dairy Farmers’ User Personas”

Part A: Scenario-Based Questions on Explainability

A1. Scenario 1

A system monitors activity data of your herd and indicates that cow No. 23 is in heat. The system recommends inseminating cow No. 23 today.

How detailed should the system justify this recommendation for you to trust it?

- I want as detailed an explanation as possible about how the system arrived at this assessment.
- I need a fairly detailed explanation with some details.
- I need an explanation without many details.
- Brief hints are enough for me.
- I don’t need any additional information besides the assessment.

A2. Which of the following explanations has the right level of detail for you to trust the system’s assessment?

- The system explains that the assessment (cow in heat) is based on increased walking activity over the last 24 hours.
- The system explains that the assessment is based on increased walking activity over the last 24 hours, which indicates restlessness and matches known patterns for heat.
- The system reports that the cow’s movement activity has increased by 40% compared to normally observed values, and lying time has decreased, which are strong indicators of heat.
- The system only indicates that the cow is assessed as being in heat.
- The system explains that the cow’s movement behavior suggests heat.

A3. The system collects and analyzes data from your farm, including sensor data, actions (e.g., administered medications), and the health status of the cows, to provide recommendations.

How precisely do you want to know how the system or the provider processes your data to trust it?

- I generally trust that providers handle my data responsibly.
- I mostly trust providers, but I would like some basic explanations about how my data is handled.
- I would feel better if I received some explanations about how my data is handled.
- I have concerns about data privacy and need detailed explanations to trust the system.
- Without comprehensive explanations of where and how my data is stored and processed, I do not trust providers.

A4. Scenario 2

A system recommends adjusting the feed ratio for your herd to include 10% more protein and 5% less fiber to improve milk quality.

How detailed should the system justify this recommendation for you to trust it?

- I want as detailed an explanation as possible about how the system arrived at this recommendation.
- I need a fairly detailed explanation with some details.
- I need an explanation without many details.
- Brief hints are enough for me.
- I don't need any additional information besides the recommendation.

A5. Which of the following explanations has the right level of detail for you to trust the system's assessment?

- The system indicates that the milk has a reduced protein concentration, while fiber intake is above the optimal level.
- The system shows a 10% decline in protein concentration over the last month and recommends a higher concentration of protein in the feed. Fiber intake is above the optimal level.
- The system only shows the recommendation to adjust the feed mixture.
- The system recommends adding protein and reducing fiber to improve milk quality.
- The system justifies the recommendation with a reduced protein concentration in the milk.

A6. The system collects and analyzes data about your farm, including feed, feed consumption, and animal health, to derive recommendations.

How precisely do you want to know how the system or the provider processes your data to trust it?

- I generally trust that providers handle my data responsibly.
- I mostly trust providers, but I would like some basic explanations about how my data is handled.
- I would feel better if I received some explanations about how my data is handled.
- I have concerns about data privacy and need detailed explanations to trust the system.
- Without comprehensive explanations of where and how my data is stored and processed, I do not trust providers.

A7. Scenario 3

A system collects and analyzes data from various sensors (e.g., body temperature, somatic cell count in milk) to provide an assessment of which of your cows are likely infected with mastitis.

How detailed should the system justify this assessment for you to trust it?

- I want as detailed an explanation as possible about how the system arrived at this assessment.
- I need an explanation without many details.
- Brief hints are enough for me.
- I don't need any additional details besides the assessment.
- I need a fairly detailed explanation with some details.

A10. Which of the following explanations has the right level of detail for you to trust the system's assessment?

- The system indicates that the cow's body temperature and somatic cell count suggest possible mastitis.
- The system justifies the assessment for the cow with an increased body temperature over the last 24 hours and an increased somatic cell count in the milk.
- The system indicates that the cow's body temperature recently rose from 38.5°C to 40.2°C, and the somatic cell count in the milk increased from 100,000 to 250,000 cells/ml.
- The system only shows the assessment that the cow is likely infected with mastitis.
- The system indicates that the cow's body temperature over the last 24 hours rose from 38.5°C to 40.2°C, exceeding the threshold of 39.5°C. Additionally, the somatic cell count in the milk increased from 100,000 to 250,000 cells/ml, exceeding the threshold of 200,000 cells/ml.

A12. How precisely do you want to know how the system or the provider processes your data to trust it?

- I generally trust that providers handle my data responsibly.
- I mostly trust providers, but I would like some basic explanations about how my data is handled.
- I would feel better if I received some explanations about how my data is handled.
- I have concerns about data privacy and need detailed explanations to trust the system.
- Without comprehensive explanations of where and how my data is stored and processed, I do not trust providers.

Part B: Demographic Information

B1. How many animals does your dairy farm have?

- Up to 30 cows
- 31 - 70 cows
- 71 - 150 cows
- 151 - 300 cows
- More than 300 cows

B2. Where is your farm located?

- Baden-Württemberg
- Bavaria
- Hesse
- Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania
- Lower Saxony
- North Rhine-Westphalia
- Rhineland-Palatinate
- Saarland
- Saxony
- Saxony-Anhalt
- Schleswig-Holstein
- Thuringia
- Other federal states: Berlin, Bremen, or Hamburg

B3. Which age group do you belong to?

- 25 or younger
- 26 to 40
- 41 to 60
- 61 or older

B4. Is your dairy farm your primary source of income?

- Yes
- No

B5. Gender

- Female
- Male
- Other

Part C: Experience and Education

C1. How many years of experience do you have working on a dairy farm?

- Up to 5 years
- 6-10 years
- 11-20 years
- Over 20 years

C2. What is your highest level of education?

- Career changer
- Agricultural training

- Higher agricultural school
- Agricultural master
- Agricultural university degree

Part D: Technology Usage

D1. How familiar are you with using software systems in your agricultural operation?

- Very familiar
- Familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Less familiar
- Hardly or not at all familiar

D2. How often do you use digital systems ("decision support systems") to make decisions for your herd?

- Currently not at all
- At most once a month
- Several times a month
- Several times a week
- Almost daily

D3. How long have you been using decision support systems (or have used them in the past)?

- Up to 1 year
- 2 - 3 years
- 4 - 5 years
- More than 5 years